

Public-Transportation Credits: The potential of three-part tariffs in public transportation[☆]

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ABSTRACT

In December 2023, public-transportation providers in Switzerland introduced Public-Transportation Credits (PTCs). PTCs are credits (or “allowances”) that are greater in amount than their price and can be used to purchase any type of public-transportation tickets within a year. With the initial fixed payment, the subsequent use of the allowance and the eventual return to the standard fare, PTCs represent three-part tariff models. We explore the potential of PTCs to target particularly elastic segments of the demand curve, simultaneously allowing for increased consumption and higher revenue. To assess the revenue impact of the PTC empirically, we analyze a pilot study conducted by the Swiss public-transportation providers. In a randomized field experiment with 200,000 PTC invitees and 911 actual PTC buyers, we use the dispatch of invitations as an instrumental variable. While observing substantial revenue increases, this result is insignificant due to the weak relationship between invitees and buyers. Therefore, we complement our analysis with a selection-on-observable approach, utilizing machine-learning techniques to match PTC buyers to customers in the control group. This way, we reveal a highly significant treatment effect, indicating a revenue enhancement of CHF 179.7 per PTC (approximately USD 200). Leveraging our comprehensive dataset and insights from a non-buyer survey, we predict a demand of around 200,000 units for the market-launch version of the PTC.

1. Introduction

Following its announcement in autumn 2022 (SRF, 2022; Alliance SwissPass, 2022), in December 2023, the association of public-transportation companies in Switzerland, “Alliance SwissPass” (ASP, henceforth referred to as “public-transportation providers”), implemented a novel pricing model. It consists of a product range which we henceforth call “public-transportation credits” (PTC).¹ For a price P_{PTC} , a customer receives an allowance of value V_{PTC} (whereas $V_{PTC} > P_{PTC}$). This non-transferable allowance can then be used to purchase a wide range of public-transportation tickets (but not season tickets) during one year. Since the PTC can be summarized by the fixed-price component, the allowance, and the (standard) fare upon completion of the allowance, it can be categorized as a three-part tariff, as defined, for instance, in Lambrecht et al. (2007).

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¹ The pricing model is marketed by the public-transportation providers under the name “Halbtax PLUS” (“Half Fare Travelcard PLUS”). See <https://www.sbb.ch/en/tickets-offers/travelcards/half-fare-travelcard-plus.html>.

Prior to fully introducing the new product range, the alliance mandated its major member, the Swiss Federal Railways (SBB) to pilot a stripped-down version of the PTC between December 2021 and March 2023 (SBB, 2021), which is the basis of the present study.²

Pricing measures in public transportation such as the introduction of the PTC are used by public-transportation providers to tackle a variety of goals—revenue optimization being only one of them. For instance, even with moderate price elasticities, lower prices allow for a higher modal share of public transportation, a typical component of performance agreements. Furthermore, and somewhat counter to the aforementioned point, by attracting former season-ticket holders, excessive zero-marginal-cost usage could be curbed—even more in times of home office gaining currency.

To varying degrees, trade-offs abound. In particular, applying the often-cited rule-of-thumb price elasticity in public transportation of -0.3 , passenger-count goals conflict with revenue goals—even in the short run, where production cost is (virtually) unaffected by increased demand.

However, according to an unpublished preliminary experimental study conducted by ASP in 2020, the introduction of a PTC actually appears to increase revenues. This is puzzling in the sense that the PTC merely introduces a new (volume) discount, which is de facto a price reduction. How is this in line with price elasticities ϵ with $|\epsilon| < 1$?

For a possible explanation, it is worth disentangling (aggregate) price elasticities into customer-specific ones. Also, some key information about the landscape of existing public-transportation tickets in Switzerland is necessary: At the end of 2021, 0.41 million out of 8.74 million people in Switzerland were in possession of a "GA Travelcard" (GA). The GA is a season ticket, covering most³ of public transportation in Switzerland.⁴ This number does not include the many more season tickets (of about 20 regional tariff networks) in circulation, which mirror the GA within a smaller perimeter. Further 2.83 million Swiss inhabitants owned a "Half Fare Travelcard" (HF), which – as the name implies – generally allows to buy tickets at half their price (SBB, 2022; BFS, 2022b).⁵

With such an unusually high "membership", all but general price movements must be analyzed with cross-price elasticities in mind—or, alternatively, public transportation may be studied as a single good with a somewhat intricate, non-linear pricing structure. This is the approach we follow in Section 3. There we argue that the current price schedule is comparatively unfavorable to customers on the brink between the HF and GA travelcard: For "heavy users", the GA is highly competitive versus the customers' major outside option, car ownership. For individuals with very low mobility needs, non-discounted tickets (combined with the HF, if applicable), public transportation stands out thanks to low fixed costs. For customers with a medium-sized mobility demand, however, public transportation is comparatively expensive against the background of today's pricing structure which in turn leads to increased price sensitivity. Consequently, a targeted price reduction in this segment can lead to above-average demand effects, potentially outweighing any decrease in yield rates. In our case, this targeted price reduction is achieved through the introduction of the PTC.

Examining the data from the pilot study, we indeed find evidence supporting a revenue-enhancing property of the PTC. While we are unable to measure demand for public transportation for all customers, we can consistently measure their expenditures.⁶ In a randomized field experiment, utilizing the distribution of pilot-study invitations as an instrument, we observe a substantial albeit statistically insignificant treatment effect. The primary reason for this insignificance lies in the weak relationship between the instrument and the treatment (i.e., the purchase of the PTC). Out of approximately 200,000 invitees, only 911 individuals purchased a PTC, with 893 completing the pilot study. However, matching these buyers with a control group built upon propensity scores yields a statistically highly significant result: On average, PTC buyers increased their yearly expenditures on public transportation by over 10 percent, rising from CHF 1680.4 to CHF 1860.1. The confidence interval of this CHF 179.7 increase ranges from CHF 115.0 to CHF 244.4. Accordingly, while the pilot study reached only a small fraction of customers, those who participated exhibited price elasticities with $|\epsilon| > 1$.

We structure the rest of our paper as follows: In Section 2, we provide a brief overview of the transportation literature concerning the impact of (targeted) price reductions, supplemented by insights from the economics literature on three-part tariffs. In Section 3, we present a theoretical overview of the PTC, discussing its impact on customers' expenditures and, consequently, public-transportation providers' revenue. In Section 4, we outline the design of the pilot study and our field experiment. We present a detailed description of the involved treatment and control groups and the collected data in Section 5. In Section 6, we present the treatment effect observed in the field experiment, while in Section 7, we extend our analysis beyond the purely experimental setting by employing matching techniques, matching the 893 PTC buyers with participants from the control group based on observable characteristics (using propensity scores). In Section 8, we explore the demand for a more "mature" market-launch version of the PTC, utilizing supplementary data obtained from a survey conducted among non-buyers from the pilot study. In Section 9, we conclude with a brief discussion of our assumptions and results, as well as recommendations for implementation.

² One of the authors worked for SBB until June 2022 as head of strategic pricing, where he conceptualized the PTC. He was granted access to the anonymized data of the complete pilot study by SBB and ASP.

³ Notable exceptions only concern touristic lines.

⁴ At the end of 2019, that is, prior to the Corona Pandemic, even 0.50 million inhabitants possessed a GA.

⁵ Also, 1.40 million children (below the age of 16) in Switzerland were automatically granted the HF price.

⁶ Given that a significant proportion of public-transportation consumption relies on season tickets, we cannot consistently measure demand in terms of passenger kilometers. Consequently, we are also unable to determine price elasticities quantitatively. However, since public transportation is not a Giffen good, we can safely assume that demand will increase with the introduction of the PTC. If revenue increases at the same time, $|\epsilon| > 1$ immediately follows.

2. Literature review

Our paper adds to the broad literature in transportation economics, analyzing the relationship between fares, demand, and revenue. As revenue effects depend on the interaction between fares and demand, empirical studies often focus on price elasticities. As mentioned in Section 1, we are not able to measure demand for all types of customers due to the prevalence of season tickets. Hence, we are also not able to compute price elasticities quantitatively. However, under very generic circumstances, a potential revenue gain arising from the introduction of the PTC (a discount) can only be explained with a (local) price elasticity with $|\epsilon| > 1$.

In the European transportation sector, (general) price elasticities are usually estimated to be below $|\epsilon| = 1$. In a meta analysis, [Holmgren \(2007\)](#) estimates short-run price elasticities of up to $|\epsilon| = 0.75$ and long-run price elasticities of up to $|\epsilon| = 0.91$, but only as long as vehicle kilometers are treated as endogenous.

In the Swiss context, a recent field experiment conducted in urban areas estimates the short-run price elasticity to be $|\epsilon| = 0.31$ ([Axhausen et al., 2021](#)). This aligns with the commonly cited rule of thumb for the price elasticity in public transportation, which is approximately $|\epsilon| = 0.3$. [Wallimann et al. \(2023\)](#) examine a price-reduction initiative in the city of Geneva, Switzerland. They find that reducing the prices of annual season tickets, day passes, and hourly tickets by up to 29 percent, 6 percent, and 20 percent, respectively, led to a 10.6 percent increase in demand over a five-year period. [Thommen and Hintermann \(2023\)](#) analyze discounts for off-peak train tickets and obtain an (own) price elasticity of $|\epsilon| = 0.7$.

Price elasticities closer to and even above $|\epsilon| = 1$ are found when limiting attention on individual submarkets and segments (as in our case): ([Kholodov et al., 2021](#)) utilize smartcard data from public-transportation systems to calculate price elasticities for distinct public-transportation modes. They find that demand for trains exhibits a larger price elasticity ($|\epsilon| = 0.90$) compared to the demand for buses ($|\epsilon| = 0.56$) and metros ($|\epsilon| = 0.45$). Additionally, they find above-average price elasticities for long-distance journeys. Isolated instances with $|\epsilon| > 1$, however, seem to be artifactual and are deemed outliers by the authors themselves. [Wardman \(2022\)](#) estimates price elasticities above $|\epsilon| = 1$ for rail trips taken for leisure purposes. Most comparable to our result is the finding of [Liu et al. \(2019\)](#), who discover revenue gains from a price reduction in Australia due to increased consumption from existing customers.

The theoretic literature on transportation economics discusses the constraints of welfare-oriented pricing.⁷ It compares first-best pricing with second-best and non-linear pricing, two-part tariffs being an prototype of the latter. A main result of the corresponding literature, which goes back to [Carbajo \(1988\)](#), states that combined tariffs prove to be more efficient than uniform fares because they allow to encourage frequent travelers' demand without forgoing revenue from infrequent users.

More recent pricing literature outside the transportation field adds to non-linear pricing by discussing the concept of three-part tariffs (e.g., [Lambrecht et al., 2007](#); [Fibich et al., 2017](#)). Such tariffs consist of a fixed-price component, the number of free units (allowance), and the price per unit above the number of free units. With customer heterogeneity, as we clearly have regarding the demand for public transportation, [Fibich et al. \(2017\)](#) show that firms should offer multiple three-part tariff plans, targeting light and heavy users separately. Hence adding the PTC "between" the HF and the GA should allow to increase revenue.

Three-part tariffs are commonly deployed in the telecommunications industry (think of mobile plans with monthly allowances of free minutes and/or gigabytes). [Ascarza et al. \(2012\)](#) examine the transition from a two-part tariff to a three-part tariff in the telecommunication market. They find that the inclusion of an allowance led to an increase in consumption beyond what might be expected from the change in their budget constraint, resulting in higher revenue. In contrast, [Malone et al. \(2014\)](#), who investigate the behavior of subscribers to three-part tariffs compared to those with unlimited plans, discover that subscribers with three-part tariffs have lower usage, particularly among heavy users. [Nevo et al. \(2016\)](#) ascertains that customers subscribing to three-part tariffs respond to the fraction of their monthly allowance used and the number of remaining days in the billing cycle.

In the transportation sector, [Caiati et al. \(2020\)](#) find that customers generally prefer three-part tariff pricing schemes over two-part tariff schemes for e-car rentals. However, it is worth noting that while their study encompasses different modes of transportation, they do not include three-part tariff options for public transportation. In addition, various studies explore mobility budgets ([Zijlstra and Vanoutrive, 2018](#); [Millonig et al., 2022](#)). Typically provided to employees, these budgets can be likened to "freemium" pricing models, which represent a specific instance of three-part tariffs with a zero-fixed-price component. While the mobility-budget literature predominantly concentrates on human-resource management and corporate sustainability, our work focuses on price incentives and revenue. Consequently, we consider our research a pioneering effort in examining the impact of three-part tariffs in public transportation.

3. Product design

In this section, we analyze the theoretical revenue effect from the introduction of the PTC based on its product design. To do so, we first examine the status quo of the public-transportation providers' pricing structure (prior to the implementation of the PTC).

3.1. Point of departure

Consider [Fig. 1](#), which presents a stylized illustration of the ticket choices available to public-transportation users in Switzerland, specifically concerning the national perimeter.⁸

⁷ For an overview, see [Hörcher and Tirachini \(2021\)](#).

⁸ Note that most of the qualitative analysis that follows is also applicable to "regional" public-transportation customers in Switzerland, who benefit from lower fares for single journeys and season tickets due to shorter distances. For the purpose of this section, we disregard travel classes and (third-degree) price differentiations among customer segments to simplify the exposition.

Fig. 1. Average expenditures with public-transportation tickets and car ownership.

Here, x refers to the amount of public transportation consumed. We describe this amount by the (hypothetical) annual expenditure for public transportation that would accrue if only non-discounted tickets would be bought.⁹ That is, $E_0(x) = x$, where $E_0(x)$ is the expenditure function regarding non-discounted tickets. The according average-expenditure function, $\bar{E}_0(x)$, is thus a flat line of height 1. $E_{HF}(x)$ refers to the expenditure function when possessing the HF, which – with an annual price tag of CHF 185 (roughly \$200) or less – is an auto include for most regular users of public transportation in Switzerland (see Section 1). The hyperbolic average-expenditure function $\bar{E}_{HF}(x)$ follows from the HF being a two-part tariff. $\bar{E}_{HF}(x)$ approaches 0.5 for $x \rightarrow \infty$. Finally, $E_{GA}(x)$ represents the expenditure function when purchasing the GA. Due to the GA only consisting of a fixed-price component, $\bar{E}_{GA}(x) \rightarrow 0$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$.

Regarding public transportation as a whole, only $\bar{E}_{PT}(x) := \min_{i \in \{0, HF, GA\}} \bar{E}_i(x)$, is relevant. For sufficiently small $x \leq \tilde{x}_{0, HF}$, non-discounted tickets (without a fixed-price component) minimize expenditure. For sufficiently large $x \geq \tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$, the GA (without a variable-price component) minimizes expenditure. In between (for $\tilde{x}_{0, HF} \leq x \leq \tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$), the two-part-tariff HF minimizes expenditure.

Note the “spike” at $\tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$. At this level of consumption, buying a GA starts getting worthwhile. But unlike at higher levels of x , at $\tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$, average expenditure with the GA equals average expenditure with the HF—a product aimed at occasional users.

Compare this to $\bar{E}_{car}(x)$, the average-expenditure curve for car owners. In general, $\bar{E}_{car}(x)$ exceeds $\bar{E}_{PT}(x)$ (BFS, 2022a). Furthermore, annual car-related expenses also consist of both fixed and variable components (comparable to two-part tariffs). The actual extent of $\bar{E}_{car}(x)$ is obviously case dependent (starting with the vehicle choice), and comparing it with $\bar{E}_{PT}(x)$ – as we do in Fig. 1 – ignores the fact that private and public transportation modes are all but perfect substitutes. However, the circumstance that $\bar{E}_{car}(x) - \bar{E}_{HF}(x)$ decreases with x and $\bar{E}_{car}(x) - \bar{E}_{GA}(x)$ increases with x indicates that public transportation is least competitive at $\tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$.¹⁰ Vice versa, by specifically approaching (potential) customers with a consumption level around $\tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$, public-transportation providers could leverage the advantage of particularly elastic demand.

As an illustration, consider the options available to public transportation to simultaneously enhance its modal share and its revenue. Price increases are clearly not viable, and so are general price decreases, as mentioned above. This leaves us with the option of isolated price decreases.¹¹

One approach is to lower the price of the GA, which could attract customers in the “critical region” around $\tilde{x}_{HF, GA}$. However, as previously observed, the GA is most competitive among customers with a very high demand for mobility. Therefore, reducing its price would primarily benefit existing customers who already heavily utilize public transportation, i.e., the inframarginal customers.

On the other hand, most HF customers rely on public transportation only occasionally. As formalized in Footnote 10, it is unlikely that car ownership would serve as a substitute for such consumption patterns.¹²

⁹ One might also interpret x as number of journeys or passenger kilometers. By using the non-discounted ticket price equivalent, however, we neither have to worry about trips of varying lengths nor do we have to take into account the (typically degressive) price function for single trips.

¹⁰ To formalize the argument: Write $E_{HF}(x)$ as $\alpha_{HF} + \beta_{HF}x$, $E_{GA}(x)$ as α_{GA} , and $E_{car}(x)$ as $\alpha_{car} + \beta_{car}x$. Then, $\bar{E}_{car}(x) - \bar{E}_{HF}(x) = (\alpha_{car} - \alpha_{HF})/x + (\beta_{car} - \beta_{HF})$, which clearly decreases in x . Similarly, $\bar{E}_{car}(x) - \bar{E}_{GA}(x) = (\alpha_{car} - \alpha_{GA})/x + \beta_{car}$ increases in x for $\alpha_{GA} > \alpha_{car}$. Since the (financial) fixed-price components of car ownership and GA ownership are of similar magnitude, $\alpha_{GA} > \alpha_{car}$ is likely to hold once non-financial opportunity costs of possessing a GA (instead of a car) are taken into account. Think, e.g., of the lack of spontaneity.

¹¹ In the following, we omit the consideration of possible price reductions for non-discounted tickets, as the argument against such a measure mirrors the one regarding the HF.

¹² It is more reasonable to assume that car ownership is already established in these cases, and public transportation is used as a supplementary mode for non-financial reasons, such as sharing a vehicle within the household or going out for some drinks.

Fig. 2. Average expenditures with public-transportation tickets (PTC included) and car ownership.

However, there are also potential customers with a mobility demand of less than (but closer to) $\tilde{x}_{HF,GA}$, who consider the current offer as relatively expensive. Part-time commuters serve as an example. The rationale behind the PTC is to specifically lower public-transportation prices around $\tilde{x}_{HF,GA}$, where the usual trade-off between yield and quantity is most likely to be suspended.

3.2. Introduction of the PTC

In our study, participants in the treatment group were given the option to purchase either a “small” or a “large” PTC, or alternatively, they could opt not to participate. While the specific details of the study design are discussed in Section 4, here we focus on describing the product from a customer’s perspective, with the large PTC as our illustrating example.¹³

With the (large) PTC, a customer pays CHF 2000 and receives a public-transportation allowance of CHF 3000 in return. This allowance is valid for 12 months and can be used for various public-transportation tickets, including single tickets and day passes. The reimbursement conditions are quite generous, ensuring that purchasing a PTC carries no financial risk: After 12 months, remaining allowance up to the price of the PTC is refunded.¹⁴

So when is it advantageous to purchase the PTC, and how strong is the incentive to do so? To simplify the discussion (and also because it is generally-speaking true), suppose that the areas of validity of the HF, the GA, and the PTC are the same. Given the above-mentioned reimbursement conditions, buying the PTC weakly dominates buying the HF. Consequently, in Fig. 2, we replace $\bar{E}_{HF}(x)$ (from Fig. 1) with $\bar{E}_{HF+}(x)$.

Up to $x = \hat{x}_1$, which equals the (upfront) price of the PTC (CHF 2000), $E_{HF}(x) = E_{HF+}(x)$, where the latter refers to the expenditure for both the HF and the PTC.¹⁵ The average expenditure $\bar{E}_{HF+}(x)$ decreases from $x = \hat{x}_1$ to $x = \hat{x}_2$, where \hat{x}_2 equals the allowance of the PTC (CHF 3000). For $x \geq \hat{x}_2$, the average expenditure of using the PTC alongside the HF remains constant. This is the case because upon a premature depletion of the PTC, one may immediately buy a new one. $\tilde{x}_{HF,GA}$ in Fig. 1, the upper bound for values of x where the HF minimizes expenditure, gets replaced by $\tilde{x}_{HF+,GA}$ in Fig. 2. Obviously, $\tilde{x}_{HF+,GA} > \tilde{x}_{HF,GA}$, because more consumption is needed to make the GA worthwhile once the PTC becomes an option.¹⁶

¹³ In brief: The small PTC costs CHF 800 and includes an allowance of CHF 1000. There are also plans to introduce an additional “intermediate” PTC with an allowance of CHF 2000 and an as-yet-undisclosed price. As there is a progressive volume discount, the exposition in this section remains applicable even with these additional PTC variations in mind.

¹⁴ For instance, if CHF 1900 of the CHF 3000 is spent, the refund amounts to CHF 100. If more than CHF 2000 is spent, there is no refund. Accordingly, there is no arbitrage opportunity.

¹⁵ Whether the HF and the PTC will be melted into a single product was yet undecided at the time of writing. The pros and cons depend on rather technical considerations, mainly regarding accounting issues. In the present discussion, we refer to the setting of the field study, where the two products were bought separately. There is no relevant distinction between the two cases as long as we assume a pro-rata reimbursement of the HF once the PTC is fully depleted, which we do in the following.

¹⁶ Consider a situation where only second-class tickets are considered. Then, for adults and as of 2023, the GA costs CHF 3860, rendering $\bar{E}_{GA}(x) = CHF\ 3,860/x$. With the PTC and the HF (with a fixed-price component of CHF 165 and a variable-price component of CHF $x/2$), for $x \geq \hat{x}_2$, the constant average expenditure equals $\bar{E}_{HF+}(x) = (CHF\ 165 + CHF\ 2,000)/(2 \times 3,000) \approx CHF\ 0.36$. By setting $\bar{E}_{HF+}(\tilde{x}_{HF+,GA}) = \bar{E}_{GA}(\tilde{x}_{HF+,GA})$, we obtain $\tilde{x}_{HF+,GA} \approx CHF\ 3,860/CHF\ 0.36 \approx 10,697$. Recall that x refers to the corresponding expenses with *non-discounted* tickets (in CHF).

Table 1
Descriptive statistic of buyers (stratification variable).

Variable	Values	Number of observations
Season-ticket ownership type	GA	106
	HF	751
	Other season tickets	13
	Non-discounted tickets	23
Age group	18–49 years	525
	49+ years	368
Region	German	708
	French	184
	Other	1

To gauge public transportation’s competitiveness vis-à-vis private transportation upon the introduction of the PTC, again pay attention to the lower envelope of the average-expenditure functions, $\bar{E}_{PT+}(x) := \min_{i \in \{0, HF, GA\}} \bar{E}_i(x)$. In Fig. 2, the shaded area highlights the difference between $E_{PT}(x)$ and $\bar{E}_{PT+}(x)$. Note that at $\bar{x}_{HF, GA}$, this difference reaches its peak. As we discussed in Section 1, it is plausible to assume that public transportation’s price advantage is lowest at this point—at least before the introduction of the PTC. Hence, as indicated by the increase of Δ , we expect that the PTC-induced price reduction specifically targets an above-average elastic fragment of the customer pool.

Before delving into the design of our study, it is important to acknowledge that the preceding deliberations are somewhat abbreviated. In particular, when it comes to participating in a pilot study, the fixed component of car-related expenditure should be considered “sunk”. Bear in mind, however, that, for $\bar{x}_{HF, GA}$ to be the maximum of $\bar{E}_{PT}(x) - \bar{E}_{car}(x)$ (see Fig. 1), it is sufficient that the annual fixed component of $E_{car}(x)$ exceeds the price of the HF, which is CHF 185 and below.¹⁷ Notably, it is plausible that a portion of $\bar{E}_{car}(x)$ is independent of x but still exhibits variability with regard to the time frame of the pilot study. Consider, for instance, parking season tickets at work and opportunity costs associated with family members lacking permanent access to the car.

4. Study design

The main goal of our study is to identify the effect of the PTC on public-transportation revenue. To do so, we randomly assigned individuals to a treatment group and a control group. Subjects in the treatment group received a personalized promo code (linked to their email address), which allowed them to participate in the pilot study, that is, to purchase either a small or a large PTC on a dedicated section of the SBB webpage. The small PTC costed CHF 800 and provided an allowance of CHF 1000, while the large PTC costed CHF 2000 and provided an allowance of CHF 3000 as a progressive quantity discount. Subjects in the control group were selected from the same customer pool (which we discuss in more detail in the following paragraph) as the subjects in the treatment group. The only structural difference between the treatment and control groups is that subjects in the control group did not receive a promo code for participating in the pilot study.¹⁸

In several respects, the pilot study differs from an actual implementation of the PTC. In the following, we briefly outline these differences, explain our countermeasures, and provide our conclusions on how these factors affect the interpretation of our results.

Accessibility

To accurately measure the demand for the PTC and understand the behavior of buyers and non-buyers, it is crucial that all eligible public-transportation ticket buyers in Switzerland have an equal chance of being included in the treatment group. This requires contacting individuals and monitoring their usage of public transportation with and without the PTC. To facilitate this, we have to focus on customers in the SBB database who have a recorded email address.

Furthermore, since the PTC is a digital product (see below), we can obtain a complete picture of its usage. To minimize bias towards the treatment group, we need to be confident to also track most of the consumption of non-buyers and individuals of the control group. To achieve this, we stipulate “online affinity” as a requirement for customers without a season ticket. This means that ticket purchases made through digital distribution channels within the past 12 months are necessary for these customers to be considered for either the treatment or the control group.¹⁹

Due to these restrictions, we stratify our sample according to socioeconomic indicators and type of ticket usage (see Table 1). As a result, we obtain representative pools for the treatment and control groups, which account for approximately 5.9 million customers

¹⁷ Using the notation of Footnote 10, $\alpha_{HF} < \alpha_{car} < \alpha_{GA}$ is sufficient for $\bar{E}_{PT}(x) - \bar{E}_{car}(x)$ to peak at $\bar{x}_{HF, GA}$.

¹⁸ Note that this assignment only applies to the randomized field experiment, discussed in Section 6. In the matching approach, which we discuss in Section 7, we construct a control group specifically for the buyers of the PTC.

¹⁹ Note that there may still be customers who mix online and offline tickets. For example, an otherwise online-savvy customer may occasionally buy paper tickets for reimbursement purposes. We have to assume that there are no systematic differences between the treatment and control groups in this respect, although offline tickets cannot be purchased with the PTC.

of Swiss public transportation.²⁰ We implicitly assume that the introduction of the PTC has a negligible impact on people that do not use (and pay for) public transportation at all in the 12 months prior to the pilot study.

Data limitations

In accordance with public-transportation providers, the pilot study is limited to a maximum of 600 PTC of each size. To account for market demand for both types of the PTC, the registration window, which opened in December 2021, closed after the first batch was exhausted in March 2022. At that point, 600 small-type PTCs and 311 large-type PTCs had been sold, resulting in a total of 911 PTCs. Up to this point, we had sent out 431,533 invitation emails to individuals in the treatment group. According to SBB, roughly 200,000 of these were opened, indicating a participation rate of 0.45%. It is worth noting that this figure does not include unopened emails, which may have been sent to recipients' junk folders. However, we believe that even after reading the email header "Travel more flexibly—take part in the pilot study", it cannot be assumed that recipients were adequately informed about the PTC.

Due to the large number of individuals who received a pilot-study invitation, it was not possible to track a year's worth of ticket sales for all of them. Specifically, for each PTC buyer, we monitor the consumption of 8 non-buyers in the treatment group, and for each tracked individual in the treatment group, we track their twin in the control group.²¹ This yields a total of $(893 \times (1 + 8)) \times 2 = 16,074$ observations.

Product features

The PTC, as it will be introduced in late 2023, can be used for a wide variety of tickets, including route and zone tickets, day passes, as well as supersaver tickets, which offer a discount of up to 70% and are only available in advance. In contrast, existing season tickets – that themselves incorporate quantity discounts – cannot be purchased with the PTC. Additionally, the PTC cannot be used for non-personalized tickets: since they can be resold, their consideration would undermine the incentive scheme described in Section 3.

The technical implementation required to enforce the above restrictions is demanding in terms of resources. Implementing these restrictions for a pilot study is at odds with the principle of a "lean product development". Fortunately, Swiss public-transportation providers offer a solution called "Automated Ticketing". This system relies on GPS-routed journeys tracked by smartphone applications. A central "price engine" combines route and zone tickets, as well as day passes, to determine a daily "best price" retrospectively (the following day). By limiting the use of the PTC to Automated Ticketing, we can eliminate the problem of non-personalized tickets and take advantage of an existing applicable ticket range.

However, by doing so, we forfeit two important features which the PTC will have at market launch: First, supersaver tickets are excluded. Second, people who do not want public-transportation providers to track their movement patterns – or dislike Automated Ticketing for other reasons, such as its impact on smartphone battery life – are less inclined to purchase the PTC in the pilot study as they will be with its final implementation.

We handle this issue in a twofold manner: On the one hand, we interpret our main results (in Sections 6 and 7) in terms of the treatment "introduction of a pilot-study PTC". In this case, the above-mentioned participation rate of 0.45% is adequate. On the other hand, we collect indicators for the eventual market demand by means of an online survey with non-buyers (from the treatment group). In Section 8, we show to what extent additional product features may raise the demand for this "market-launch PTC".

There are even more arguments (which we also discuss in Section 8) which let us assume that penetration of the market-launch PTC substantially exceeds the one of the pilot-study PTC. In some instances, however, we manage to control for altering product features preemptively in the study design. Notably, due to the short decision window of two weeks, we would expect that GA holders refrain from buying a PTC in the pilot study due to existing GA refund conditions. With the definitive launch, on the other hand, they can defer their purchase to the moment their GA expires, circumventing any financial loss. To take this into account, refund conditions were overwritten for the pilot study. Specifically, buyers of the PTC were allowed to refund their existing season tickets "pro rata temporis", which was also advertised in the invitation email. This way, at least the financial consequences for potential buyers who were not allowed to wait for the renewal date of their season ticket could be eliminated.

With the aforementioned considerations in mind, we can now approach the evaluation of the pilot study. As our main interest concerns the overall revenue impact from implementing the PTC, we gather the entirety of (personalized) sales across all sales channels. For instance, even customers who use the PTC might buy additional tickets (for touristic travel outside the area of validity), or they benefit from additionally purchasing a regional season ticket.

The observation period is observation-specific. For buyers (and their twins from the control group), the period starts on the first day of validity of the PTC and ends with the last day of validity, that is, 364 days later. For non-buyers (and their twins), we proxy equivalent dates by the (elapsed) purchase deadline. Thus, observations started between December 2020 and March 2021 and ended between December 2022 and March 2022. Owed to the yearlong individual observation periods – and as we assume that there are no interaction effects between season and PTC lifecycle – we do not have to control for seasonality.

²⁰ We exclude children below the age of 18 and seniors above the age of 80 due to practical reasons. We also exclude residents of the Italian-speaking part of Switzerland, who constitute 6 percent of the Swiss population.

²¹ We speak of "twins" when describing observations with identical values of the stratification variable (see Table 2). We perform stratification only to increase the statistical power when determining the effect sizes in Sections 6 and 7. Note, however, that we do not perform individual matching (in Section 7), but propensity score matching, where the complete control group is taken into account for each buyer.

Table 2
Description of control variables.

Variable	Description
Expenditures (total)	Sum of expenditures on season tickets and single tickets
Expenditures (single tickets)	Sum of expenditures on single tickets
Ticket type	Stratification variable (see Table 1)
Spread	Maximum value of a expenditures on single tickets minus minimum value of expenditures on single tickets
Spread (months)	Maximum monthly sum of expenditures minus minimum monthly sum of expenditures
CV	Coefficient of variation (standard deviation divided by mean) of expenditures on single-tickets
CV (months)	Coefficient of variation of monthly sum of expenditures
Trips	Number of single-ticket purchases
Trips (first class)	Number of first-class single-ticket purchases
Age	0–99
Gender	Male/female

Table 3
Means (standard deviations) of buyers and control group.

Variable	Buyers	Control group (unbalanced)	Control group (balanced)
Ticket type (GA, first class = 1)	0.02 (0.13)	0.01 (0.09)	0.02 (0.13)
Ticket type (GA, second class = 1)	0.10 (0.30)	0.09 (0.28)	0.11 (0.32)
Ticket type (HF = 1)	0.72 (0.45)	0.50 (0.50)	0.65 (0.48)
Ticket type (HF + other season ticket = 1)	0.12 (0.33)	0.11 (0.31)	0.12 (0.33)
Ticket type (other season ticket = 1)	0.01 (0.12)	0.14 (0.35)	0.05 (0.23)
Ticket type (non-discounted tickets = 1)	0.03 (0.16)	0.15 (0.35)	0.04 (0.20)
Age	46.98 (13.78)	43.90 (16.18)	44.61 (14.63)
Gender (female = 1)	0.43 (0.50)	0.54 (0.50)	0.51 (0.50)
Region (German = 1)	0.79 (0.41)	0.75 (0.43)	0.75 (0.43)
Previous Expenditure (total)	1585.24 (1213.67)	834.57 (1028.88)	1475.78 (1180.66)
Previous Expenditure (single tickets)	614.93 (613.51)	169.77 (323.19)	577.80 (603.42)
Spread	37.15 (27.88)	16.59 (23.65)	36.34 (29.52)
Spread (months)	188.87 (125.16)	75.26 (88.23)	176.17 (123.05)
CV	0.63 (0.38)	0.36 (0.42)	0.62 (0.40)
CV (months)	0.66 (0.43)	0.54 (0.62)	0.66 (0.46)
Trips	44.66 (46.40)	14.26 (28.21)	43.34 (47.66)
Trips (first class)	4.59 (14.38)	1.09 (6.26)	4.75 (14.07)
Expenditure (Outcome)	1860.11 (1091.42)	955.27 (884.57)	

To compute total revenue, we add up individual expenditures for tickets. In the case of (mostly season-) tickets with validity periods starting or ending outside the observation period, we compute the share of the validity period as a fraction of the observation period and truncate expenditures accordingly.

Regarding the PTC, recall from Section 3 that a remaining allowance is refunded up to the price of the PTC. Using E_{PTC-T} for ticket expenses met with the PTC, P_{PTC} for the price of the PTC and V_{PTC} for its value (size of the allowance), we compute PTC-related expenditures as:

$$E_{PTC} = \begin{cases} \sum E_{PTC-T}, & \text{if } \sum E_{PTC-T} \leq P_{PTC}, \\ P_{PTC}, & \text{if } P_{PTC} < \sum E_{PTC-T} \leq V_{PTC}, \\ \frac{365}{T} \times P_{PTC} & \text{if } \sum E_{PTC-T} > V_{PTC}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the final case of Eq. (1), T refers to the number of days it takes to deplete the PTC. Instead of separately adding up ticket expenditures after this point in time, we act as if such a buyer would immediately buy another PTC of the same size. Even though this was not possible in the course of the pilot study, it would be the sensible thing to do. Note that Eq. (1) is in line with Fig. 2 in Section 3. Specifically, the immediate renewal of the PTC corresponds to the constant average expenditure \bar{E}_{HF+} between \hat{x}_2 and $\hat{x}_{HF+,GA}$.

5. Descriptive statistics and consumption patterns

592 costumers of our final dataset bought the small PTC, whereas 301 customers bought the large PTC (cp. Section 3). At the outset of the pilot study, 84.1 percent of the PTC buyers owned an HF and 11.8 percent a GA. 1.5 percent of the PTC buyers held one or more other travel cards, and 2.6 percent traveled with non-discounted tickets. In the control group, 60.1 percent of the customers owned a HF, 9.5 percent a GA. 15.2 percent possessed other travel cards and 14.5 percent traveled with non-discounted tickets. We summarize the season-ticket ownership type as well as some socioeconomic indicators of PTC buyers in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Temporal consumption patterns of all PTC buyers (left-hand panel) and the reduced sample (right-hand panel).

During the pilot study, the PTC buyers (of both types) spent on average CHF 1860.10, including expenditures on the PTC as well as on other tickets. Non-buyers in the treatment group spent on average CHF 948.75, customers in the control group CHF 955.25.

However, already prior to the pilot study, PTC buyers spent more on public transportation than customers in the control group. While PTC buyers spent on average CHF 1585.25 during the year prior to the field experiment, non-buyers in the treatment group spent on average CHF 823.70, customers in the control group CHF 834.55.²²

Obviously, we cannot simply compare yearly expenditures of the buyers in the treatment group with customers of the control group to determine the revenue impact of the PTC. This is because individuals with high propensities to consume public transportation arguably self-select into the buyer group.²³ In Sections 6 and 7, we identify strategies to construct more apt comparison groups for the PTC buyers.

However, the data on PTC expenditures provides evidence that suggests a consumption-boosting impact of the PTC. Fig. 3 illustrates the daily PTC expenditures during the pilot study. In the left-hand panel, we show the daily means for all PTC buyers ($N = 893$).

These values exhibit the highest levels during the first four months of the pilot study. This may be explained by the fact that we cannot observe further PTC expenditures from buyers whose allowances have been fully depleted.

To address this, in the right-hand panel of Fig. 3, we narrow down our sample to customers who have not spent more than 11/12 of their allowance during the first 11 months of the pilot study. In this reduced sample ($N = 493$), we observe an increase in the mean daily expenditure towards the end of the pilot study. Specifically, while the average daily PTC expenditure from weeks 3 through 50 is CHF 3.24, this value rises by 31% to CHF 4.25 during the last two weeks.

This observed “catch-up effect” suggests that the PTC stimulates consumption.²⁴ However, it is evident that this consumption stimulus is limited, as we observe many PTC buyers who do not fully take advantage of their “free” tickets: In Fig. 4, we group PTC buyers based on the relation between their expenditures and the PTC price and allowance.

Notably, we observe that many purchasers of the large PTC do not exhaust their allowance fully. This behavior aligns with a scenario of highly inelastic public-transportation demand: The large PTC becomes the rational choice with an anticipated PTC consumption of more than only CHF 2200.²⁵ Consequently, we expect a considerable proportion of “large PTC” buyers whose anticipated consumption level falls between the price (CHF 2000) and the allowance (CHF 3000).

However, on a scenario without the PTC, these customers might have spent less than CHF 2000 on public transportation. Hence, even if they do not strongly react to zero-marginal cost tickets during the pilot study, these customers might well exhibit high price elasticities at initial purchase of the PTC.

To thoroughly disentangle these partially contradicting effects, it is best to globally compare a situation with the PTC to counterfactual scenarios without it. This comparison is precisely what we undertake in the following two sections.

6. Randomized field experiment

In our field experiment, approximately 200,000 randomly selected public-transportation customers received an invitation to participate in the pilot study. 893 of these treated individuals used the attached promo code, purchased the PTC, and completed the pilot study. This indicates that the majority of customers did not comply with the random treatment assignment and chose not to participate in the pilot study. It is important to acknowledge that the customers who purchased the PTC (referred to as “buyers”) and those who did not (referred to as “non-buyers”) may have systematic differences in unobserved characteristics. Therefore, while

²² Recall that the year prior to the pilot study marked the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic.

²³ For a comparison of the buyer group and the control group, see Table 3 in Section 7.

²⁴ Note the sharp initial increase in PTC expenditures in both panels of Fig. 3. This pattern can be explained by the fact that PTC buyers initially continued to use their previous season tickets during the early days of the pilot study. There are various scenarios that render this behavior economically beneficial, even with the generous refund conditions explained in Section 4.

²⁵ With an expected consumption of between CHF 800 and CHF 2200, the small PTC (including a “bonus” of CHF 200) becomes more favorable.

Fig. 4. Temporal consumption patterns of all PTC buyers (left-hand panel) and the reduced sample (right-hand panel).

the assignment to the treatment group was randomized, the purchase choice may be confounded. To assess the revenue impact of the PTC based on the dispatch of invitations, we must account for imperfect compliance (Imbens and Rubin, 2015).

In our case, we utilize a binary variable $Z \in \{0, 1\}$ (which takes the value 1 when an invitation was sent to the customer) as an instrument for our explanatory variable $D \in \{0, 1\}$ (which takes the value 1 for "compliers", i.e., customers who purchase the PTC when given the opportunity). This approach allows us to consider different customer types that may differ in terms of unobserved characteristics.

Let us denote E as a customer's yearly public-transportation expenditure, our variable of interest. Since we observe E for compliers in the treatment group, we can estimate $\mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 1]$ without bias. To account for unobservable factors, we need to compare E for compliers in the treatment group with (would-be) compliers in the control group. However, participants in the control group did not receive an invitation, so we have to indirectly derive $\mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 0]$. This requires two assumptions to be met within an instrumental-variable approach.

The first of these assumption, stating that D and Z are statistically independent, is satisfied by design. Accordingly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[E|Z = 0] &= \mathbb{P}(D = 0, Z = 0) \times \mathbb{E}[E|D = 0, Z = 0] + \mathbb{P}(D = 1, Z = 0) \times \mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 0] \\ &= \mathbb{P}(D = 0, Z = 1) \times \mathbb{E}[E|D = 0, Z = 0] + \mathbb{P}(D = 1, Z = 1) \times \mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 0] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The second assumption states that Z does not affect E except through D . Consequently, in Eq. (2), we can substitute the unknown quantity $\mathbb{E}[E|D = 0, Z = 0]$ with $\mathbb{E}[E|D = 0, Z = 1]$.²⁶ This substitution renders the right-hand side of Eq. (2) with a single unidentified term, $\mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 0]$, which represents the counterfactual expenditure of buyers in the absence of the pilot study.

By straightforward rearrangement, we can express the treatment effect of the randomized field experiment as

$$\mathbb{E}[E|D = 1, Z = 1] - \frac{\mathbb{P}[E|Z = 0] - \mathbb{P}[D = 0, Z = 1] \times \mathbb{E}[E|Z = 1, D = 0]}{\mathbb{P}[D = 1, Z = 1]}.$$

However, it is worth noting that the sample largely consists of "never takers", resulting in minimal variation in the treatment D between the treatment and control groups. Therefore, our instrument is weak and may explain only a small portion of the variation in E , leading to potentially very noisy estimates. To reduce this noise, we only consider the part of E that is not explained by previous expenditures. In other words, we regress E on the expenditure of the year before the pilot study and calculate the point estimate with the resulting residuals.

Moreover, since we only have a subsample available and cannot rely on conventional instrumental variable approaches to estimate the treatment effect, we calculate 95% bootstrap confidence interval. This involves randomly drawing subjects with replacement from our subsample 2000 times and then estimating the effect in every bootstrap sample.

Using this approach, we estimate an average treatment effect of CHF 925.5. However, this point estimate is statistically insignificant. The 95% bootstrap confidence interval ranges from CHF -3108 to CHF 4815. As expected due to weak correlation between the instrument "invitation" and the PTC purchases, our instrument is too weak to draw conclusive inferences regarding the impact of the PTC on expenditure and revenue.

²⁶ Participants with $D = 0$ and $Z = 1$ are considered "never takers" as they did not purchase the PTC despite having the opportunity to do so. Clearly, they would also refrain from purchasing the PTC if they did not have the chance (cf. Huber, 2023).

Fig. 5. Distribution of propensity scores.

7. Matching

To complement our analysis of the experiment's findings, we incorporate a matching approach. Instead of relying solely on the random invitation as an identifying factor, we match the 893 study participants with similar customers in the control group based on observable characteristics. That is, we aim to compare customers with similar characteristics but different treatment states (D).

Compared to the randomized field experiment of Section 6, we have to assume conditional independence, implying that we have observed and accounted for all variables that jointly influence both E and D .²⁷ Fortunately, as outlined in Table 2, we have access to a comprehensive dataset that allows us to not only control for personal characteristics but also consumption patterns in the year prior to the pilot study. It is important to note that all control variables refer to information collected before the start of the pilot study, ensuring that they are not influenced by the treatment in a way that is related to the outcome (i.e., exogeneity of confounders).

Matching approaches balance the treatment and control groups with respect to conditional treatment probabilities, referred to as propensity scores. This way we are able to balance the control group in such a way that it structurally resembles the treatment group. We exemplify this balancing in Table 3, which presents descriptive statistics of our matching variables for the treatment group, the unbalanced control group and the balanced control group, respectively.

Fig. 5 presents the distribution of the propensity scores, with a notable number of customers having propensity scores close to zero. It is important to ensure that the probability of buying a PTC must fall strictly between 0 and 1, indicating that the assignment mechanism is not deterministic.

To implement matching, we employ the causal forest, as described by Athey and Wager (2019), due to its functional flexibility in capturing non-linear dependencies. We utilize the *grf* package developed by Tibshirani et al. (2018) developed by Hothorn et al. (2015) in the statistical software *R*. Specifically, we calculate the overlap-weighted average treatment effect, recommended by Li et al. (2018), which is particularly suitable when the propensity scores of one group are close to zero.

We obtain an average treatment effect of CHF 179.7. The 95% confidence interval ranges from CHF 115.0 to CHF 244.4, signifying a statistically significant point estimate.

We benchmark our estimated effect using linear regression. As the regression Table 5 in Appendix A shows, the OLS treatment effect amount to CHF 202.2, being significant at the 1% level.

In Table 4, we summarize our results. Note that, despite not explicitly leveraging the randomization of the invitations in the matching approach, the interpretation remains the same as with the randomized experiment—that is, as long as purchasing the PTC is random conditional on the control variables.

8. Market potential

In Section 4, we mentioned that the participation rate of 0.45% only applies to the “pilot-study PTC” but is highly likely to underestimate demand for the PTC after market launch. The PTC's appeal will extend beyond the above-mentioned inclusion

²⁷ In our case of panel data, the use of the conditional-independence approach instead of the difference-in-differences approach is suggested by Imbens and Wooldridge (2009).

Table 4
Effect of PTC on expenditure.

	Randomized field experiment	Matching	Linear regression
Treatment effect	925.5 ^a	179.7	177.4
Standard error	1984.44 ^a	33.02	21.92
p-value	0.638 ^a	0.000	0.000
Number of observations	16,074	8930 (thereof: 893 buyers)	

^a Values computed with bootstrapping ($N = 2000$).

of supersaver tickets.²⁸ It will offer enhanced accessibility through various sales channels, not limited to Automated Ticketing. Furthermore, additional improvements will be implemented, such as the introduction of an “intermediate” PTC and discounted prices for young individuals. Importantly, potential customers will have the opportunity to purchase the PTC outside of a test environment, eliminating the requirement of participating in market research. This will allow for more time to deliberate, better understanding of the product, and exposure to promotions and word-of-mouth advertising, among other factors.

To evaluate the market potential, the public-transportation providers conducted an online survey specifically targeting members of the treatment group who opted not to purchase the PTC. Within this survey, a total of 273 participants provided reasons for their decisions and revealed which altered product features would persuade them to buy the PTC. Based on these and other criteria,²⁹ in conjunction with the planned design of the final PTC, the public-transportation providers reached the conclusion that approximately 6.3% of non-buyers from the pilot study are likely to change their minds upon the official launch of the product.

Using the same algorithm as the public-transportation providers, we are able to replicate this finding (see Table 6 in Appendix B). However, as an attempt to correct for self-reporting and self-selection biases, we propose two correcting measures.

First, we match the individual respondents’ stated preferences with the propensity score, as described in Section 7. The propensity score, which summarizes the likelihood of buying a PTC, can be matched with the contact data of 218 out of the 273 respondents. We compare the distribution of these 218 values with those of all non-buyers from the treatment group (a total of 7144 available records), enabling us to calibrate the sample once again. Specifically, we compute weights by comparing population ratios (regarding all non-buyers) with sample ratios (regarding survey respondents).³⁰ This allows us to recognize that self-selection occurred to a considerable extent. The lowest bin (representing those least likely to buy a PTC) consists of only 7 individuals surveyed, while each of the top 3 bins (representing those most likely to buy a PTC) includes 35 to 37 respondents.

Second, we argue that stated preferences of potential PTC customers are only credible when supported by corresponding consumption patterns. Specifically, we require their propensity scores to be within the interval of the top 95% of actual PTC buyers. By combining this requirement with the post-stratification weights from the previous steps, we conclude that only 45.4% of the respondents possess propensity scores that align with those of PTC buyers. Taking this into account alongside their self-reported willingness to buy, we determine that 2.92% of non-buyers are ultimately likely to purchase the market-launch PTC. Adding this to the actual buyers (0.45% of the population), the estimated market demand becomes $[0.45\% + (1 - 0.45\%) \times 2.92\%] \times 5.9 \text{ m.} \approx 198,000$ customers.

Some reservations remain, however. First, the prediction of 2.92% of non-buyers expected to convert into buyers is based on a small sample size of only 218 interviews, resulting in a mere 7 individuals (unweighted) who are likely to change their minds. As a result, the forecast carries a high level of uncertainty. To emphasize this point, we performed a bootstrap analysis using 5000 samples of the 218 survey respondents (with replacement). Fig. 6 illustrates the density of the resulting distribution, which exhibits a clear positive skew. The corresponding 95% bootstrap confidence interval spans from 63,230 to 479,060 customers.

The second caveat pertains to revenue-related conclusions. We refrain from extrapolating the findings of Sections 6 and 7 to the market expansion from the pilot-study PTC to the market-launch PTC. This extrapolation could only be justified if the improved product features would solely impact the demand for the PTC but not the behavior of buyers. However, it cannot be precluded that the latter will be influenced as well.

9. Discussion and conclusion

In our study, we first presented theoretical arguments for the application of three-part tariffs in public transportation as a means to simultaneously increase demand and revenue. By considering the price–quantity structure and competitive environment, we demonstrated that introducing a product between two-part tariffs (the HF) and season tickets (the GA) can effectively address particularly elastic demand.

Empirically, we supported this hypothesis by analyzing the pilot-study for the PTC, a three-part tariff set to be introduced in Switzerland in December 2023. Employing a randomized field-experiment approach, our findings yielded point estimates aligned with the revenue-enhancing argument. However, these estimates are not statistically significant, potentially due to a “weak

²⁸ Note that the inclusion of supersaver tickets not only affects demand, but also the yield. In the following, we ignore this circumstance based on the public-transportation providers’ statement that supersaver tickets are (at least) revenue-neutral as compared to regular tickets.

²⁹ Other criteria included the perceived attractiveness of the PTC and the level of understanding of the product.

³⁰ Following Sturges’ rule ($\text{number of bins} = \lceil 1 + \log_2(N) \rceil$), we compute these ratios for 9 equally populated intervals.

Fig. 6. Probability distribution of the demand for the market-launch PTC (vertical lines indicate the 95% confidence interval).

instrument” issue arising from the low participation rate of only 0.45% among invitees who received an e-mail offer to participate in the pilot study.

To enhance the statistical power of our analysis, we applied the conditional-independence assumption (CIA) and constructed a comparison group by matching PTC buyers with individuals from the control group based on observable characteristics. While the resulting revenue increase of CHF 179.7 is highly significant, the CIA is crucial: For instance, it may well be the case that some customers self-select into the treatment group based on their (unobservable) prospects. Consider changes in life circumstances which we cannot observe. For instance, if moving to a new residence leads to an increase in both the willingness to pay for public transportation and the likelihood to purchase a PTC, the CIA may be compromised, potentially leading to an overestimation of the treatment effect. Since the pilot study was conducted during the Covid-19 recovery (with the baseline data from the midst of the pandemic), life circumstances underwent changes for nearly everyone, making the possibility of such a violation non-negligible. However, to a certain extent, our comprehensive data set also allows us to control for the responses to the pandemic: As Table 2 shows, we included predictors such as the variation coefficient and the spread of expenditure between months in the year preceding the pilot study. Since during the baseline year there were also months with barely any Covid restrictions in Switzerland, the reaction to the Covid-19 recovery is not entirely unaccounted for.

Finally, we endeavored to predict market demand for the PTC upon its official launch. To achieve this, we had to rely – at least partially – on self-reported purchase intentions of non-buyers in the pilot study. Given the circumstance that the market-launch PTC will differ from its pilot-study counterpart, our point estimate of approximately 200,000 demanded PTCs per year has to be taken with a grain of salt.

To address all the uncertainties mentioned above, closely monitoring customer behavior in the initial years following the PTC’s launch and making necessary adjustments to both the analytical and empirical models, as well as the PTC itself, will be crucial.

Beginning with the analytical model, there is potential to expand the nascent research on three-part tariffs with competitive elements (in our case: competition between modes). Formally endogenizing modal choice could also facilitate a comparison of prices set by public-transportation providers with first-best prices from a utilitarian standpoint. Presently, our results only suggest an augmented combined rent in the public-transportation market due to the implementation of the PTC, as customers’ loosened budget constraints coincide with providers’ higher contribution margins. To make statements on societal welfare, however, a consideration of various factors would be needed, ranging from congestions and emissions to crowding issues and the public financing of infrastructure. Notably, unlike traditional season tickets and recently increasingly experimented-with (almost) fare-free transportation, the PTC is neither particularly well-suited for commuters nor does it encourage excessive demand. Assuming that induced additional (leisure) trips are more likely to occur in underutilized vessels, at least our abstraction from (step-fixed) costs seems justifiable.

Transitioning to recommendations for additional empirical research, first note that our study contributes to the pricing-elasticity literature by framing the demand for public transportation as a function of the specific price structure. Although the quantitative measurement of elasticities is impeded in our case by the absence of universal consumption data (as opposed to expenditure data), we can derive qualitative conclusions regarding ‘local’ elasticities.³¹ We advocate for capitalizing on the growing accessibility of consumption data to obtain more nuanced insights into price elasticities.

³¹ Note that while public-transportation providers measure passenger kilometers through frequency surveys, these data are only available at an aggregate level. Computing elasticities concerning specific pricing measures (as opposed to general price adjustments) would require micro-level data or, at least, distributional information.

Table 5
Linear regression, as a benchmark for the matching approach described in Section 7.

	Coefficient	Standard error	t-value	p-value
<i>(Intercept)</i>	428.17	62.51	6.85	0.00
<i>Ticket type (GA, first class = 1)</i>	1572.42	94.51	16.64	0.00
<i>Ticket type (GA, second class = 1)</i>	733.26	62.47	11.74	0.00
<i>Ticket type (HF + other season ticket = 1)</i>	182.98	58.10	3.15	0.00
<i>Ticket type (HF = 1)</i>	-126.41	55.74	-2.27	0.02
<i>Ticket type (other season ticket = 1)</i>	-308.42	57.55	-5.36	0.00
<i>Ticket type (other season ticket = 1)</i>	72.92	57.58	1.27	0.21
<i>Age</i>	-1.51	0.39	-3.85	0.00
<i>Gender (female = 1)</i>	-37.84	12.00	-3.15	0.00
<i>Region (German = 1)</i>	4.11	14.19	0.29	0.77
<i>Previous Expenditure (total)</i>	0.58	0.01	49.44	0.00
<i>Previous Expenditure (single tickets)</i>	0.20	0.05	4.34	0.00
<i>Spread</i>	0.89	0.57	1.58	0.12
<i>Spread (months)</i>	0.49	0.11	4.53	0.00
<i>CV</i>	13.76	29.62	0.46	0.64
<i>CV (months)</i>	89.60	12.45	7.19	0.00
<i>Trips</i>	1.58	0.45	3.52	0.00
<i>Trips (first class)</i>	4.65	0.87	5.35	0.00
<i>Treatment effect</i>	202.23	21.76	9.29	0.00

Table 6
Stated preferences (market potential).

	Proportion (<i>N</i>)	Proportion, weighted ^a (<i>N</i>)
At least one affirmative response to “I would buy a PTC if the following were true” (actual improvements from pilot study ^b)	61.2% (167)	65.0% (177.2)
“Use by several people” explicitly not mentioned as “I would buy a PTC if the following were true”	60.8% (166)	59.5% (162.3)
Not having refrained from the pilot study because of not understanding the PTC	93.4% (255)	93.1% (254.1)
PTC rated as attractive (at least 6 out of 7 points)	31.1% (85)	35.3% (96.3)
Not having refrained from the pilot study because of “too small” or “too large” PTCs	52.0% (142)	44.5% (121.3)
Conditions cumulatively met	4.8% (13)	6.3% (17.3)

^a Weighting according to the stratification variable listed in Table 2.

^b Improvements: PTC can be purchased not only online; PTC is not registered to Automated Ticketing; PTC can be used for supersaver tickets; PTC at other sizes available; PTC can be used for other ticket types such as first-class upgrades; positive testimonials available.

Regarding the product itself, further differentiation is welcome as far as compatible with customer ease of use. This could involve offering additional discounts for different customer groups or introducing additional allowance packages, such as the scheduled “intermediate” PTC. As for future steps and potential adoption by other countries, we suggest staying on the exploratory path involving tests, pilot studies and a gradual market launch.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Silvio Sticher: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kevin Blättler:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Appendix A. Linear regression (benchmark)

See Table 5.

Appendix B. Stated preferences (market potential)

See Table 6.

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